

Synthesis, characterization and spectral studies of lanthanide(III) nitrate complexes of 10-[(1-methyl-3-piperidyl)methyl]phenothiazine

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Eight coordinated lanthanide(III) nitrate complexes with 10-[(1-methyl-3-piperidyl)methyl]phenothiazine (Mepazine) having the general formula $[\text{Ln}(\text{MZ})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$ (where Ln = La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho, Er, Tm, Yb, Lu and MZ = Mepazine), have been prepared and characterized by analytical, conductance, infrared, electronic and magnetic studies. The complexes show 1 : 1 electrolytic behavior. Mepazine acts as a bidentate ligand, the heterocyclic nitrogen atom and tertiary nitrogen atom of the side-chain being the sites of coordination. Only two of the nitrate groups are coordinated bidentately to the central metal ion while the other remains uncoordinated.

Phenothiazines possess various biological activities¹. They find applications in industry² and chemical analysis^{3,5}. Biologically active complexes of copper(II), dioxouranium(IV) and tantalum(V) with phenothiazines have been reported⁴. In this paper, we report the synthesis, characterization and spectral studies on complexes of lanthanide(III) nitrates with mepazine.

Results and Discussion

The reaction of lanthanide nitrates in aqueous solution with mepazine hydrochloride in methanol yields lanthanide(III) nitrate-mepazine complexes. The stoichiometries of the complexes proposed are supported by analytical, magnetic and molar conductance data (Table 1). All the complexes are stable at room temperature, non-hygroscopic and do not possess sharp melting points. They are soluble in DMF and DMSO but insoluble in water and common organic solvents.

The molar conductances (in DMF) values of the complexes ($82\text{--}99 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) indicate their 1 : 1 electrolyte behaviour. The magnetic moment values for all the complexes except those for La and Lu indicate their paramagnetic nature as expected for lanthanide(III) complexes. The measured magnetic moments show a little deviation from Van Vleck values⁵ thereby indicating that the 4f-electrons do not participate in bond formation. The data also suggest there is no metal-metal interaction or spin-spin coupling.

Infrared spectra : It was reported that the ion R_3NH^+ combined with Cl^- present in *N*-alkylphenothiazines give rise to a broad band at $2500\text{--}2300 \text{cm}^{-1}$. A broad band at $2570\text{--}2500 \text{cm}^{-1}$ observed in the spectra of mepazine hydrochloride corresponds to $\text{CH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_9\text{NCH}_3\text{H}^+$ combined

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of lanthanide(III) nitrate complexes*

Compd.	Ln% : Found/ (Calcd.)	μ_{eff} B.M.	NO_3^- (ionic)**
$[\text{La}(\text{MZ})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	14.55 (14.68)	Dia	0.0327 (0.0328)
$[\text{Ce}(\text{MZ})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	14.68 (14.79)	2.60	0.0328 (0.0327)
$[\text{Pr}(\text{MZ})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	14.71 (14.86)	3.65	0.0328 (0.0327)
$[\text{Nd}(\text{MZ})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	14.98 (15.16)	3.75	0.0326 (0.0326)
$[\text{Sm}(\text{MZ})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	15.60 (15.71)	1.85	0.0324 (0.0323)
$[\text{Eu}(\text{MZ})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	15.72 (15.84)	3.50	0.0321 (0.0321)
$[\text{Gd}(\text{MZ})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	16.21 (16.31)	6.75	0.0322 (0.0321)
$[\text{Tb}(\text{MZ})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	16.48 (16.45)	9.45	0.0319 (0.0320)
$[\text{Dy}(\text{MZ})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	16.68 (16.76)	10.03	0.0318 (0.0319)
$[\text{Ho}(\text{MZ})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	16.82 (16.97)	10.30	0.0320 (0.0319)
$[\text{Er}(\text{MZ})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	17.20 (17.17)	9.60	0.0317 (0.0318)
$[\text{Tm}(\text{MZ})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	17.40 (17.31)	6.95	0.0317 (0.0317)
$[\text{Yb}(\text{MZ})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	17.63 (17.65)	5.03	0.0316 (0.0316)
$[\text{Lu}(\text{MZ})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	17.68 (17.81)	Dia	0.0314 (0.0315)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

**Sample taken for determination = 0.5 g.

with Cl^- ion. In the spectra of the corresponding lanthanide(III) complexes, these bands either disappeared or reduced to a small hump showing that tertiary nitrogen atom of the side-chain is a site of coordination. Bands observed at $2860\text{--}2825 \text{cm}^{-1}$ of the mepazine hydrochloride may be due to the heterocyclic nitrogen atom attached to the alkyl group. In the spectra of the corresponding lanthanide(III) complexes, this band disappeared completely suggesting the coordination of the heterocyclic nitrogen atom. This shows that mepazine acts as a bidentate chelate with heterocyclic nitrogen atom and tertiary nitrogen atom of the

side-chain as two coordination sites.

The sharp band at 755 cm^{-1} (CSC)⁶ observed in the spectra of mepazine hydrochloride remained unaffected in the spectra of the corresponding lanthanide complexes supporting the non-coordination of heterocyclic sulphur atom.

It can be seen that ir spectra of the lanthanide nitrate complexes exhibit four bands around $1486\text{--}1480$, $1290\text{--}1280$, $1038\text{--}1030$ and $825\text{--}820\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which can be assigned to the vibrational modes of the coordinated (C_{2v}) nitrate groups. The magnitude of splitting of two bands at higher energies ($200\text{--}196\text{ cm}^{-1}$) suggests that the nitrate groups are present as bidentate ligands⁷. The bands observed at $1388\text{--}1378\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are due to ionic nitrate present in the complexes. The far-ir spectra of the complexes exhibit new bands at $445\text{--}440\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to $\nu_{\text{Ln-N}}$ modes⁸. This shows that these complexes have both ionic and coordinated nitrate groups.

Electronic spectra : In the electronic spectrum of mepazine hydrochloride the $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions are observed at 31746 and 39370 cm^{-1} respectively. In the corresponding complexes the $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ band blue-shifted to $32786\text{--}32467\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ band red-shifted to $38023\text{--}36764\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The electronic spectra of $f\text{-}f$ transitions for the Pr^{III} , Nd^{III} and Er^{III} complexes in the visible region and their tentative assignments^{9,10} are given in Table 2. These bands showed an appreciable red-shift with respect to the corresponding aqua-ions. Various bonding parameters have been calculated using appropriate equations^{9,11}. The values of nephelauxetic ratio (β) are smaller than unity and the values

of bonding parameter ($b^{1/2}$) and Sinha's parameter ($\delta\%$) and covalency angular parameter (η) suggest covalency in the metal-ligand bonding¹². These parameters also indicate a weak covalency for metal-ligand bond¹³.

Thermal studies : The thermal studies indicate that all the lanthanide(III) complexes are stable upto 250° which shows that there are no coordinated water and solvent molecules. The complexes underwent two-stage decomposition in the range $270\text{--}350^\circ$ with weight-loss of $63.2\text{--}65.6\%$ due to the organic moiety and at $370\text{--}750^\circ$ with weight-loss of $18.0\text{--}19.5\%$ due to nitrate followed by the formation of lanthanide(III) oxides. The residue became constant at 770° . The DTG studies show that both the decomposition of organic moiety and formation of lanthanide(III) oxides are exothermic processes.

It is concluded that two mepazines and two nitrate groups are bound to the lanthanide ion and another nitrate group is in the outer coordination sphere. Hence the present complexes may be formulated as $[\text{Ln}(\text{MZ})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$. The lanthanide ions in the complexes exhibit coordination number eight.

Experimental

The nitrates of La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Tb and Dy (Indian Rare Earths Ltd.) and Ho, Er, Tm, Yb and Lu (Aldrich) were used. Mepazine hydrochloride was obtained from Byk Gulden Pharmaceutica. Methanol, ether, DMF and DMSO were of AnalaR grade.

Preparation of complexes : A mixture of aqueous solu-

Table 2. Electronic spectral data and related bonding parameters of the complexes

Ln^{III}	$\lambda_{\text{max}} (\text{cm}^{-1})$	Complex	J-level	$(1-\beta)$	β	$b^{1/2}$	$\delta\%$	η
Pr^{III}	22222 21276 20408 16949	$[\text{Pr}(\text{MZ})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	$^3H_4 \rightarrow ^3P_2$ $\rightarrow ^3P_1$ $\rightarrow ^3P_0$ $\rightarrow ^1D_2$	0.0055	0.9945	0.0524	0.5530	0.0027
				0.0067	0.9933	0.0578	0.6745	0.0033
				0.0098	0.9902	0.0700	0.9896	0.0049
				0.0080	0.9920	0.0608	0.7455	0.0037
Nd^{III}	19607 17241 13513 12500	$[\text{Nd}(\text{MZ})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	$^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow ^2G_{9/2}$ $\rightarrow ^4G_{5/2}, ^2G_{7/2}$ $\rightarrow ^2S_{3/2}, ^4F_{7/2}$ $\rightarrow ^4F_{5/2}, ^4H_{9/2}$	0.0049	0.9951	0.0494	0.4924	0.0024
				0.0082	0.9918	0.0640	0.8267	0.0041
				0.0075	0.9925	0.0612	0.7556	0.0037
				0.0080	0.9920	0.0651	0.8064	0.0040
Er^{III}	20408 18867 15384	$[\text{Er}(\text{MZ})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	$^4I_{15/2} \rightarrow ^2H_{11/2}$ $\rightarrow ^4S_{3/2}$ $\rightarrow ^4F_{9/2}$	0.0056	0.9944	0.0529	0.5631	0.0028
				0.0077	0.9923	0.0620	0.7759	0.0038
				0.0085	0.9915	0.0651	0.8572	0.0042

tion of lanthanide(III) nitrate (except La and Ce) (2.5 mmol) and methanolic solution of mepazine hydrochloride (6.0 mmol) was refluxed on a water-bath for ~2 h and then cooled in an ice-bath. The resulting solid complexes were washed with methanol and dried under reduced pressure over fused calcium chloride. Complexes of La and Ce were prepared by mixing the corresponding nitrates with mepazine hydrochloride in aqueous medium. The complexes precipitated immediately were washed with water and dried as above.

Elemental analysis (C, H and N) were performed on a Carlo-Erba 1106 analyser. The metal content was determined by complexometric EDTA titration¹⁴ and ionic nitrate gravimetrically using nitron reagent¹⁵.

Magnetic moment was determined by Gouy method at room temperature using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as the calibrant. Molar conductance of the complexes was measured using an Elico CM-82T conductivity bridge. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu FT-IR 470 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (in DMF, 10^{-3} M solution) on a JASCO-UVIDEK-610 spectrophotometer. Thermal analysis were carried out on a Rigaku-TGA instrument with a linear heating rate of $10^\circ \text{ min}^{-1}$ in static air.

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